

Abstract

Oral interactional feedback has been found effective in enhancing learners' second and foreign language acquisition (see Lyster, 2004b and Bell, 2008); many questions were left unanswered, however. The present research was conducted to answer some of these questions. It compares the effects of prompts and recasts on enhancing learners' production of two complex English grammatical structures, namely, conditionals and relatives.

Four groups of Syrian Arab EFL learners were engaged in form-focused activities about the target structures over a three-week period- a quasi-experimental study which depended on testing and uptake, response to feedback, as two outcome measures. The learners were provided with either prompts (feedback that prompts learners to modify their output) or recasts (feedback which reformulates learners' erroneous utterances) in response to their erroneous conditionals and relatives. The results showed that although prompts led to more output pushing than recasts, both types of feedback were equally effective in improving learners' acquisition of conditionals and relatives (as partial knowledge) and they had ample opportunities to enhance learners' production of such structures in a form-focused learning context. However, no relation was found between uptake frequency and feedback effectiveness on the posttest.

It is pedagogically implied that foreign language teachers should be theoretically informed about interactional feedback to know how to deal with any errors expected from EFL learners' production of complex structures. Language teachers have also to consider the factors influencing the communicative orientation of the language classroom. Moreover, incorporating complex structures in form-focused designed syllabi would make different kinds of interactional feedback easily noticeable by learners as negative evidence targeting their errors.